
ACCESS TO SUSTAINABLE ENERGY: A PANACEA TO RURAL HOUSEHOLD POVERTY IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Energy is critical to achieving virtually all the Millennium Development Goals. Whether it is electricity for schools or clinics, energy for the delivery of health, education and sanitation, services, clean fuel to reduce indoor pollution, energy for pumping water or heat for cooking food and boiling water, energy in all its forms will be required to achieve these ends. Current patterns of energy consumption are polluting and unsustainable, and are characterized by inequity in consumption and access. Finding appropriate energy solutions that will fuel economic growth and increase social equity is essential. Energy is one of today's most serious issues. It is one of the most complexes. Satisfying the needs of hundreds of millions of people living in subsistence conditions has implications for international policy and economic relations as well. This is particularly pressing for developing countries like ours, since economic development-vital if millions are to be helped out of poverty-requires greater use of energy for their numerous farm operations. This paper thus argues that access to secure energy is one of the pre-requisites for rural poverty reduction in Nigeria and examines the energy crisis facing Nigeria and issues pertaining to use and consumption. It is divided into five sections, section one is the introduction which sets the ball rolling by providing the background information. The second section discusses the energy crisis in Nigeria, while section three outlines the energy issues facing Nigeria. In section four, the energy needs of rural Nigerians were outlined with their major applications while in section five; we discussed the ways/strategies for tackling challenges to sustainable energy service delivery.

KEYWORDS: Energy, poverty, renewable, solar, rural dwellers, Nigeria,

INTRODUCTION

Energy is an essential ingredient for socio-economic development and economic growth. The objective of the energy system is to provide energy services. Energy services are the desired and useful products, processes or indeed services that result from the use of energy, such as for lighting, provision of air-conditioned indoor climate, refrigerated storage, transportation, appropriate temperatures for cooking etc. The energy chain to deliver these cited services begins with the collection or extraction of primary energy, which is then converted into energy carriers suitable for various end-uses. These energy carriers are used in energy end-use technologies to provide the desired energy services (Sambo, 1997; Sambo, 2005).

From the foregoing, it is clear that energy is an essential input to all aspects of modern life. It is indeed the life wire of industrial production, the fuel for transportation as well as for the generation of electricity in conventional thermal power plants. The situation was such that nations were complacent with the oil dominated scenarios of the 1950's and 1960s during which time regular and reasonably cheap supplies were available. However, oil producing countries caused a world-wide reaction by deciding to increase the prices of crude oil in the early seventies. Of course, the oil-rich countries like Nigeria recorded tremendous economic gains. On the other hand, those developing nations that did not have oil were subjected to serious economic problems as they suddenly found themselves utilizing. In some cases, up to 50% of their foreign exchange earnings for importing petroleum products or crude oil in order to sustain their oil-based industries and public utilities (Sambo, 1992).

Currently a high proportion of the world's total energy output is generated from fossil fuels such as oil and coal. In general, the quest for an option to conventional power schemes for extension to remote and rural locations of developing countries like Nigeria arises from the high costs associated with the extensions, as well as the maintenance of the power grid system to rural areas. The costs of grid extensions will vary widely from country to country and will be heavily dependent on the system used, the length of connection required the type of topography, the usage pattern and the load factor of the supply point (Charters, 1985, Sambo, 2005).

More specifically, the close relationship between the proximity of energy resources to the potential users coupled with the high cost of conventional energy sources have led to a considerable interest in the development and application of renewable energy resources. Although research and development activities are still being seriously undertaken in various aspects of renewable energy utilizations, a number of the technologies have since been shown to be feasible and ready, for adoption into the economy. These technologies are very suitable for the rural areas of Nigeria (Sambo, 1991).

The lack of adequate energy services in rural areas of developing countries has social dimensions as well as serious environmental and health effects. Many of these problems are exacerbated by the almost exclusive reliance of rural populations in most areas on traditional fuels coupled with simple technologies characterized by low energy efficiency and harmful emissions. (Goldemberg, 2000). The second half of the 20th century witnessed a strong urbanization trend and the emergence of megacities (those containing more than 10 million people) in most developing countries. Between 1970 and 1990 the share of people living in cities grew from 28 to 50 percent. But while the rural population relatively decreased during this period, the absolute number of people living in rural areas increased to 3 billion. Despite this, rural development often remains low on government agendas because of increasing demands of growing, politically and economically dominant urban populations. Thus the explosive growth of cities makes it difficult for policy-makers to give rural development the attention it deserves.

The dispersed character of rural populations and their low commercial energy consumption result in poor capacity utilization efficiency for transmission and distribution systems and other energy infrastructure. Extending an electric grid to a few households in a rural setting can result in reduced energy costs per kilowatt-hour, seven times the cost of providing electricity in an urban area. Thus conventional approaches to extending energy infrastructure are economically inefficient, for both public and private providers-which is another reason the energy problems of rural populations are given low priority by governments. (Goldemberg, 2000).

Because the poor people in rural areas lack access to electricity and modern fuels, they rely primarily on human and animal power for mechanical tasks, such as agricultural activities and transport, and on the direct combustion of biomass (wood, crop residues, dung) for activities that require heat or lighting. Human energy is expended for household work (gathering and preparing biomass for fuel, fetching water, washing clothes), agriculture, and small industry. Biomass fuels are typically used for cooking (which dominates inanimate energy consumption most warm regions), space heating, heating water for bathing and meeting some industrial heating needs. Kerosene is used predominantly for lighting, and to a small extent in rural industry. Although much of the world's rural population has no access to electricity generation, many have small battery- operated devices such as radios and flashlights. (Goldemberg, 2000).

Large amounts of human energy are spent gathering fuel wood in many parts of the world, and the burden tends to fall more heavily on women and children. Although there are exceptions, history has generally shown that when alternatives are available and affordable, consumers opt for more modern energy carriers. As incomes rise and opportunities for using better technologies become available, consumer preferences shift to more efficient, convenient, cleaner energy systems as they become more affordable. That is, consumers move up the energy ladder. This involves a shift to modern energy carriers or to more convenient and energy-efficient conversion devices

For cooking and other heating purposes, the lowest rungs on the energy ladder involve use of dung or crop residues, with fuel wood, charcoal, kerosene, and liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) or natural gas representing successively higher rungs. For lighting, the lowest rung is represented by fire, followed in turn by liquid-fuelled (such as kerosene) lamps, gas lanterns, and electric bulbs. To do mechanical work, consumers shift from human and animal energy to diesel fuel and electricity as soon as they become available, because they are almost always more cost-effective. Often a synergy between modern energy carriers and more efficient end-use devices occurs.

Accelerating the introduction of modern energy, then, is a key strategy for promoting sustainable development in rural areas of developing countries. Principally, it involves providing:

- Clean liquid or gaseous fuels for cooking, and electricity for lighting and other basic household amenities.
- Liquid fuels and electricity to mechanize agriculture.

- Electricity sufficiently low in cost to attract industrial activity to rural areas (thereby providing well-paying jobs and helping to stem migration to urban settlements).

Progress in delivering modern energy to rural areas has been slow. But as will be shown, technical options to provide rural people with access to convenient, affordable energy services are commercially available (or nearly so). This is particularly the case in regions where modern energy carriers, such as biogas or producer gas, can be derived from local biomass and where gathering biomass feed- stock can provide opportunity for income generation. The challenge of making modern energy available to the very poorest households is primarily institutional, notwithstanding the economic costs and risks inherent in developing and disseminating untried systems.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

Poverty is wide spread and affects over 70 percent of Nigerians living mostly in rural areas whose main occupation is farming. Despite governments' efforts to reduce or alleviate poverty, it is still on the increase day by day. The paper thus argues that access to sustainable energy is a pre-requisite for rural poverty reduction. It outlines the various areas sustainable energy is of importance for rural poverty reduction and development.

METHODOLOGY

This paper is a review and as such is based on a desk review of available literature. Data were obtained mainly through the web search and it is presented primarily for raising awareness and policy discussion.

ENERGY CRISIS IN NIGERIA

Poverty is widespread among Nigeria's over 148 million inhabitants. In 1980, 28 percent of the population was considered poor. Today, 71 percent live on less than one dollar a day, while 92 percent live on less than two dollars a day (UNDP, 2006). Poverty in the Niger Delta is higher than the national average, with about 70 percent of the population having no access to basic services (Clean Water, electricity and medical services). Yet the Niger Delta accounts for 90 percent of national exports and 70 percent of government revenue, mainly from oil and gas (Idemudia, 2006). A survey of community needs posted on the Delta State website found that respondents demand improved access to energy more than any other service. This survey included respondents from the nine Niger Delta States (Shaad and Wilson, 2009). As a country with vast oil and gas reserves, abundant sunlight and significant hydropower potential, Nigeria should not be suffering an energy crisis. The energy sector is characterized by missed opportunities and wastage, due to poor regulation, lack of maintenance, and entrenched corruption. Inadequate power generation and transmission, limited access to the national grid, and generator fuel costs are persistent problem for nearly every Nigeria (Shaad and Wilson, 2009).

For most Nigerians, cooking is the most important energy need. Sixty-seven percent of the population uses wood or charcoal as a cooking fuel. Wood fuel cooking is inefficient and is believed to be responsible for about 79,000 deaths annually from indoor air pollution. Kerosene is also used for cooking, but is polluting, hazardous and expensive. People also tend to prefer the taste (and experience) of food cooked on a fuel wood stove. In urban areas, the cost of fuel wood is increasing. In rural areas, the cost of fuel wood is increasing. In rural areas, fuel wood gathering takes 3-6 hours per day unsustainable use of fuel wood also contributes to deforestation.

About 60 percent of Nigeria's population has no access to electricity (90 percent in rural areas) (Shaad and Wilson, 2009). People need power for lighting (e.g. for evening study); household appliances, irrigation pumps, health clinics (e.g. vaccine refrigeration) food and agricultural processing (e.g. cassava driers and rice mills); and transport fuel. Small-scale traders, manufacturers and craftspeople also require power for small-scale machinery, such as sewing machines.

Lighting is the most expensive energy need. The poorest African households may spend 10-15 percent of their income on kerosene lamps or candles.

Nigeria's poorest households earn 1-2 US dollar per day, but they spend on average 0.40 US dollar per day on their energy needs (Hammond *et al.*, 2007). Kerosene lamps provide poor lighting and are expensive, inefficient, highly polluting and dangerous. Contaminated and low quality kerosene is widely available on the black market. Kerosene prices fluctuate with the rise of oil. Small diesel generators are an option for those with sufficient cash, but these carry high fuel costs and require maintenance. They produce polluting fumes and noise and they often generate excess unused power. For a small business, generator costs can represent a major

portion of overheads, which is stifling the development of small-scale enterprise in the country. The cost of energy is blamed for the collapse of the textiles and auto manufacturing industries in Northern Nigeria. Firms have relocated to Lagos where power supplies, though intermittent, are more reliable (Malik *et al.*, 2004).

Unsustainable fuel wood gathering puts Nigeria's forests under pressure, particularly in the North. This has led to desertification, drought, arid land and a decline in crop production. These combine with the regional effects of climate change: a drop in the water table and a decline in rainfall (FAO, 2005). Gas flaring also has significant negative impacts on the environment, not least due to its climate change impacts. Associated gas has been flared since the start of oil production in the Niger Delta. Nigeria flares about 2.5 billion cubic feet (over 70 million m³) of gas per day, (or 40 percent of its annual gas production, which is 12.5 percent of all globally flared gas). This amounts to about 70 million tones of carbon dioxide (UNDP/World Bank, 2004). Gas flares release toxic substances, including benzene and particulates, which damage the human immune system and increase the acidity of rain. Health risks include child respiratory illness, asthma and cancer. Households that rely on traditional livelihoods such as fishing and crop production have suffered due to negative impacts on fish and vegetation.

The failure of national electrification in Nigeria over the last three decades is attributed to corruption, poor maintenance and uncompleted projects. Of Nigeria's 79 power stations, most of which date from the 1970s and 1980s, only about 15 are currently working-often not to full capacity (The Economist 2007). The country's demand for energy is a estimated 7,600 megawatts, (MW). However its total installed generating capacity is only 6,000MW. The government has set by mid-2009, with a total of 20,000MW achievable by 2011. Most power generation comes from three conventional sources: hydropower, coal (Thermal) and diesel or gas fired power plants. These currently account for the intermittent generation of 3,500MW, or about 20 watt per person.

Electricity transmission is a major problem in Nigeria. The centralized grid system is dependent on large-scale generation, and considerable amounts of energy are cost in transmission. The government acknowledged the need for greater investment in decentralized power generation, but still priorities infrastructure for centralized generation.

ENERGY ISSUES IN NIGERIA

The major energy issues in Nigeria can be conveniently categorized as inefficient energy utilization, inefficient and unreliable energy supply system, environmental concerns, energy financing, inadequate technological capabilities in the energy sector and weak institutional framework (World Energy Council, 1993). However, before discussing these issues, there is need to consider the current energy consumption patters of the country.

Energy consumption patterns

In 1991 the Sokoto Energy Research Centre, at the instance of the Energy Commission of Nigeria, carried out a survey of 55 Local Government Areas in Niger, Kano, Katsina and Sokoto States as well as in the Federal Capital Territory., Abuja. The report of that survey (Sambo, 1991) as well as the report of similar surveys carried out in other parts of the country can be summarized as follows:

- a) Agricultural Sector: Human and animal power provide the bulk of the energy requirements for agricultural production. As assessment of the energy unit adopted, that is man hours, showed that sharp variations exist in the magnitudes of the man hour figures from place to place. Evidence of use of petroleum products for agricultural production has been recorded. This, though small when compared with human and animal power, is significant because it showed the use of motorized irrigation pumps and diesel powered tractors for mechanized agricultural activities (Sambo, 2005).
- b) Household Sector: Fuel wood was found to be the predominant energy source in the household sector with about 70-80% of households depending on its as their cooking fuel in both the remote villages and the towns. The consequences of this to the natural environment is that unchecked felling of trees to provide the fuel wood requirements will exacerbate desert encroachment, soil erosion and loss of soil fertility problems. In the interim it would not be practical to stop the sue of fuel wood rather the short term solution is the adoption of efficient wood.-burning stoves together with the widespread establishment of fast growing trees. In the long term one would suggest the introduction of other fuels like LPG, kerosene and smokeless coal briquettes to replace the use of fuel wood (Sambo, 2005). Kerosene is the predominant energy source used in the rural areas for lighting. There is strong evidence of the use of small quantities of kerosene is

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- d) Assist the quick commencement of combustion of fuel wood. This is in addition to its use in the urban centres as a cooking fuel. The predominant type of lantern used, is the wick-type which does not produce a good level of luminosity. The third energy type in terms of significance in the household sector is electricity which is mostly limited to state and Local Government Headquarters and some big towns. Most of the electricity in the rural areas is provided by the State Rural Electricity Boards (Sambo, 2005).
- e) Industrial Sector: Electricity from NEPA dominates the energy supply for the industrial sector. This is supplemented by electricity generating sets that are fueled by automotive gas oil (diesel). High and low pour fuel oils are used in textile, cement and brick manufacturing plants. The foregoing is for large industries which are mostly located in the big cities and towns, for the small towns and villages, the bulk of the small-scale industries are operated on diesel generators for bakeries, small-scale steel works, small-scale ceramic/pottery works etc. In these localities other small-scale activities like handicraft, weaving etc are based on human power.
- f) Transport Sector: In the transport sector, prime motor spirit (Petrol) is the major fuel for saloon cars and the 'small buses'. For lorries, trucks and rail transport the predominant fuel is automotive gas oil (diesel) while for air transport the fuel is aviation kerosene. It has been estimated that 74% of the petroleum products demand of Nigeria is for the transport sector with only 19% for the industrial sector. Of the amount of fuel consumed in the transport sector, 50% is absorbed by passenger transport by air (Sambo, 1997).
- g) Services Sector: In remote rural areas, human power is used for water lifting from wells while in the big villages and many towns, diesel powered pumping systems are relied upon to lift water from boreholes, Hospitals and health centres in rural areas rely on both REB-generated electricity and diesel generators for lighting, sterilizing of appliances as well as for storage of drugs and vaccines. Use is made of fuel wood and to a lesser extent LPG, for cooking. The situation in the health centres is very much the same in boarding schools, barracks and prison houses.

Inefficient Energy Utilization

Presently, energy utilization in Nigeria is far from being efficient. Apart from the direct loss due to energy wasted, using energy inefficiently has three major implications in Nigeria. These are:

- a) The investment in some energy supply infrastructure is far in excess of what the energy demand is;
- b) The environmental problems associated with energy utilization are more aggravated due to large energy consumption; and
- c) Excessive energy consumption adds to the costs of goods produced especially in energy intensive industries like cement, steel works and refineries.

The potential for energy savings is substantial in the three most energy consuming sectors of the economy namely household, industry and transportation. In the households sector, for example, there is considerable energy loss due to the use of inefficient traditional three stone stoves with efficiencies of between 5 to 12%. Efficiencies three times that can be obtained. In the household sector substantial savings can be made by simple switching over from incandescent bulbs to fluorescent lamps. In the industrial sector energy audit studies have shown that up to 25% of energy consumption can be saved by adopting simple housekeeping measures. Each measured include putting off electrical machinery on no-load condition, plugging steam leaks and avoiding material wastages. In the transport sector, major savings can be realized by emphasizing mass transit schemes.

The major barriers militating against the adoption of more energy efficient practices in Nigerian can be dignified as follows:

- a) Lack of awareness of the potential and importance of energy efficiency.
- b) Lack of skilled manpower to carry out energy audit studies, and
- c) Lack of awareness of potential alternatives such as renewable energy technologies.

Inefficient and unreliable energy supply system

In electric energy supply efficiencies of existing thermal plants are low. They are as low as 12% whereas efficiencies of up to 40% are attainable with modern technologies. Also substantial electricity is lost during transmission and distribution. These losses are sometimes more than 30% of the total electricity generated. Apart from these inefficiencies the reliability and availability of existing installed electric generation system is

low. There is the serious problem of power unreliability over the years such that most industrial establishments and upper income households install very expensive generating sets amounting to over half of the total installed grid capacity. This constitutes huge economic losses to the Nigerian economy.

The major factors contributing to the above unreliability and inefficiency in the power sector are:

- a) Frequent breakdown of generating plants and equipments due to inadequate repairs and maintenances.
- b) Lack of foreign exchange to purchase needed repair parts on time.
- c) Obsolete transmission and distribution equipment which frequently breakdown.
- d) Lack of skilled manpower, as well as
- e) Inadequacy of basic industries to service the power sector.

In the petroleum sector, production, marketing and distribution system are often inadequate, inefficient and costly. On the production side, refinery capacity utilization is generally low largely due to operation and maintenance problems.

Environmental Concerns

The major environmental problems related to energy production, distribution and consumption are deforestation, air and land pollution as well as flooding. Excessive fuel wood consumption arises due to population growth, low technical efficiency of the traditional three stone stoves and the lack of adoption of other sustainable cooking methodologies. These contribute to deforestation which is a very serious issue because they serve as sinks for carbon dioxide, maintenance diverse plants and animal life and also regulate the flow of water. Their loss, as mentioned earlier, leads to soil erosion, desert encroachment and loss of soil fertility (Sambo, 2005)

Combustion of fossil fuels, especially in the transport and industry sectors, contributes greatly to air pollution in cities. A major air pollution that poses health hazards to both dwellers of the cities and rural areas is the long exposure to smoke from biomass combustion in poorly ventilated kitchens. Major water and soil contamination are reported from time to time which arise from oil spillages in the oil producing areas of the country. Dams for hydropower have been noted to periodically cause flooding of agricultural land upstream while at the same time the dams cause destruction of the ecology downstream.

Other issues

The other important issues include poor energy financing, low technical capabilities in the energy sector and weak institutional framework. The energy sector is a large consumer of national resources, demanding large capital expenditures, skilled manpower and steady foreign exchange out flows. Almost invariably, energy financing has been the exclusive prerogative of government whose own capacity to finance new investments is inadequate. Low technical capacity is responsible for the nation's inability to manufacture components of power plants as well as to maintain the various units of the energy sector. The main problem with institutional framework in the energy sector is the fact that the linkages between the various energy institutions are rather weak.

The Need to Re-address Our Priorities

An analysis of the country's energy resources base will clearly show that the nation stands to benefit immensely by ensuring that petroleum products are made to last for as many years to come as possible so they continue to serve as revenue earners and also to enable fueling of the industrial sector for as many years to come as possible. This can only be realized after the adoption of as many energy types as possible within the energy mix of the country. The clear and practical approach is to adopt the renewable energy sources of solar, biomass, wind energy and small-scale hydropower plants for as many applications as possible. This approach is supported by the fact that all or at least two renewable energy sources are available in all parts of the country, the technology for their use is mostly simple and for which the capacities exist; their use does not require the heavy financing and they are not associated with serious environmental implications. As a matter of fact these considerations were long thought of and brought to bear by the federal government which established, amongst others, two energy research centres for research and development in renewable energy.

ENERGY NEEDS IN RURAL AREAS

In general, the energy needs in the rural and semi-urban areas of Nigeria can be categorized as follows:

A. Domestic Needs

- ⇒ Cooking
- ⇒ House lighting
- ⇒ Domestic water pumping and distribution
- ⇒ Television and radio powering Water heating
- ⇒ Refrigeration

B. Agricultural Production

- ⇒ Water pumping and distribution for irrigation
- ⇒ Operation of various agricultural equipment or implements
- ⇒ Processing and storage of agricultural products
- ⇒ Drying

C. Community Needs

- ⇒ Hospitals, Clinics
- ⇒ Schools
- ⇒ Barracks, prison houses etc.

D. Industrial/Commercial Needs

- ⇒ Small to medium industries
- ⇒ Business establishments (shops, banks, restaurants, bakeries etc).

Major Applications of Renewable Energy and Technology for Local Adoption

A. Solar Energy

There are many solar thermal systems especially solar water heaters and solar dryers in use in many parts of the country. Solar cookers, solar stills, solar chicken brooders and solar thermal refrigerators developed by research centres and confirmed to be of practical applications. However solar photovoltaic applications have wider current installation in the country and these include solar photovoltaic water pumping systems, solar powered vaccine refrigerators as well as telecommunication repeater stations that are powered by solar photo-voltaic. There are also solar photovoltaic power plants that are providing electricity to entire villages and also others that are powering on stand-alone basis, some specific projects such as rural health centres television viewing centres.

B. Biomass

Many versions of efficient wood-burning and charcoal stoves have been developed and are being used in many parts of country with the overall objective of curtailing the amount trees that are perennially cut to provide fuel wood and char-coal. Biogas digesters, which are capable of producing biogas that could be used for domestic and industrial uses, have been developed in many parts of the country.

C. Wind Energy

Wind energy used to be relied upon in the 1950s and 1960s for provision of water in many locations of the northern part of the country. However this was largely abandoned when the development of petroleum products reached advanced stages. The development of the Poldow wind pump in Bauchi using locally available materials is surely a move in the right direction. Of course it should be mentioned that there are a few modern wind water pumps in some parts of the country. There is also one wind electricity generator currently supplying electricity from wind energy at Sayya Gidan Gada in Sokoto State.

Renewable Energy Technologies Ready for Local Adoption

A large number of renewable energy devices have been developed by Nigerian researchers in various parts of the country (Sambo, 1991). These devices which are ready for incorporation into the economy especially for rural areas include:

A. Solar Cookers

These are box-type arrangements where most local dishes can be cooked within one hour under average sunshine conditions.

B. Solar Water Heaters

The heaters which are based on fiat-plate collectors with appropriate storage units can produce water at temperatures of up to 80°C will find applications in hospitals, hotels, industry and private residences and are capable of significant reduction of electricity bills.

C. Solar Dryers

Both portable cabinet dryers, for individual private use, as well a large-scale units, for community utilization, have been developed. The dryers which typically attain temperatures of up to 60-70°C are suitable for drying a variety of agricultural produce.

D. Solar Stills

Solar stills are designed produce distilled water from brackish water and will be useful for hospitals, industry and laboratories. When sized appropriately they can provide for the needs of comprehensive health centres of semi-urban localities.

E. Water Pumping

Many workers have demonstrated the use of photovoltaic solar modules for pumping water from wells and boreholes especially in rural areas for providing the water requirements of entire communities. Photovoltaic powered pumps can also be employed for irrigation purposes.

F. Storage of Vaccines and Drugs

Photovoltaic power components have also been shown to adequately provide the electricity for refrigerators and deep freezers in which vaccines and drugs can be safely stored without losing their potencies.

G. Street Lights and Traffic Controllers

Photovoltaic modules have been used to provide uninterrupted electricity during the day and night for traffic controllers in city centres. With the use of storage batteries they have also been shown to power street lights continuously without the power outages commonly associated with the mains supply.

H. Improved Wood-Burning Stoves

Clay-based improved cool stoves, of various designed, have been developed and these conserve the amount of fuel- wood consumed by up to 50%, lead to faster cooking and with the attachment of chimneys they allow for organized exit of smoke and consequently reduce smoke inhalation.

I. Production of Biogas

With biogas digesters, which are typically constructed from sheet metal or empty drums and fed with slurries of animal dung they can produce biogas and after 2-3 days. This gas which has a reasonable content of methane is combustible and can be relied upon for the production of gas for domestic cooking. ii can also be used for powering internal composite engines for electricity generation in rural areas.

J. Wind for Electricity Generation

In Nigeria, for quite some time, only laboratory trials have been made in the area of using wind for electricity generation. Such trails have been made with models of three-bladed aero turbines and the results obtained indicate the potential for stand-alone utilization especially in the Sahelian zone as well as the coastal areas of the country. Recently, however, an increasing number of wind water pumping sets and wind electricity conversion systems have been installed.

K. Electricity from Micro hydro Systems

The generation of electricity from numerous waterfalls and rivers in the form of micro hydro plants for integration into the national grid as well as for stand-alone utilizations, iii remote locations, is a system that has been shown to be viable.

STRATEGIES FOR IMPROVEMENT AND TACKLING CHALLENGES TO SUSTAINABLE ENERGY SERVICE DELIVERY

A) solar energy

The thrust of the policy here should be the incorporation of solar energy devices into as many spheres of the economy as possible. The strategy for this include:

- ⇒ Continuous active support of research and development activities to cater for site specificity of designs for all parts of the country.
- ⇒ Support of demonstration and pilot projects to ensure that the general public become aware of the potentials of solar energy technology which will as well assist in creation of markets for solar energy systems.
- ⇒ The provision of financial incentives to encourage the use of solar energy systems particularly in rural areas where the greatest potential exist.
- ⇒ The introduction of regulatory measures to encourage and protect local capabilities.

b) Biomass

The policy outline above for solar energy also applies here. Further it should be emphasized that fuel wood consumption rate should be significantly reduce. Strategies for this are:

- ⇒ The adoption of efficient wood-burning stoves
- ⇒ Systematic cultivation of fast growing trees needed to facilitate the regeneration of forests.
- ⇒ The active introduce of biogas digesters to cater for the cooking energy needs of especially large households and institutions like boarding schools, hospitals, barracks, prison houses etc.
- ⇒ The development of alternative technologies to supplement wood both as a domestic energy source and also as a building/furniture material.

c) Wind Energy

The policy and strategies for solar energy are also applicable here. Additionally, the policy should emphasize the exploitation of wind energy for rural water supply and also for electricity generation. That is to say the additional strategies are:

- ⇒ Aggregate drive to optimize the components of wind water pumping and electricity generation and-to de-emphasize diesel powered water pumps wherever the wind speed will allow wind water pumping.

d) Hydropower

The policy here is for the nation to manage its water resources for the development of its hydro-electric potentials and for other uses. The policy should focus more on micro-hydro plants. The additional strategy includes the initiating and updating of data on the potentials of small-scale hydro plants and the preparation of inventories for their locations.

e) Promotion of rational and efficient energy use

To achieve of more rational and efficient energy utilization we must ensure that wastages in energy use are reduced, energy efficiencies of major energy supply systems are improved considerably and a more energy efficient development path is pursued. For these to be realized the following strategies are required:

- ⇒ Creation of awareness for the benefits of energy savings in all sectors of the economy.
- ⇒ Encouraging households to shift to more energy efficient fuels such as LPG to kerosene in place of fuel wood.
- ⇒ Promoting the use of improved cooking stoves.
- ⇒ Providing incentives for energy intensive industries to invest in industrial energy efficiently measures and human resources development in the area of energy conservation.

f) Provision of energy security for rural dwellers

One of the major needs of rural dwellers is the energy they consume for subsistence and because they lack access to commercial fuels like petroleum products and electricity they depend largely on traditional fuels mainly fuel wood, charcoal and agricultural residues. In order to provide the energy needs of rural dwellers, especially in the sahelian zone of the country. The following measures are necessary:

- ⇒ Continued Afforestation programme
- ⇒ Setting up of community, based wood lot programmes
- ⇒ Accelerated rural electrification schemes.
- ⇒ Promotion of energy efficiency practices.

g) Integration of environmental consideration into energy development plant

Because of the strong energy-environment linkage it is important to integrate the policies affecting the two sectors for sustainable development. This can be done by incorporating environmental considerations during the planning and execution stages of large conventional energy projects. The requirements for this include:

- ⇒ Improving forestry management by strengthening the institution charged with monitoring forestry resources;
- ⇒ Incorporating environmental impact assessment for all major energy projects.
- ⇒ Internalized the external cost in pricing energy products
- ⇒ Designing and enforcing guidelines for monitoring the environment.

Tackling Challenges To Sustainable Energy Service Delivery

To be more effective at addressing development issues in general, including energy poverty, there is need to focus on actual local needs, rather than responding primarily to political pressure. For this, the following issues should be addressed:

Encourage local ownership and involvement

It is important to involve local communities in a meaningful way in the design and implementation of interventions. This also has the benefit of reducing the potential for conflict and of ensuring long-term local commitment and fostering a sense of local ownership over initiatives. Local ownership by entrepreneurs and local authorities is essential to ensure that a pilot initiative can be scaled up into a long-term sustainable business. The enterprise process needs to be aligned with people's own desires and aspirations; it needs to be something that they will be able to operate and manage themselves in the future. Many sustainable energy technologies are not widely available to communities and as a result they frequently do not understand the options available. Technical assistance by development partners to support promotion and adoption of appropriate technologies is crucial.

Empower and build the capacity of communities

Local capacity building is essential for the long-term success of interventions. This ranges from training local communities in installation, maintenance and business skills; to establishing local financial services; to institutional capacity building within government and community institutions for strategic market development. In addition to technology transfer and maintenance, training is also needed to build capacity for local manufacture and assembly of equipment and spare parts. Entrepreneurial networks and associations can be useful for building and exchanging skills and experience, it is also important to prepare local consumers for using new types of technology, engaging in minor maintenance and overcoming financial challenges.

Support community-based models for energy service delivery Community-based models have great potential but require significant investment of time and skills development. A community-based enterprise might be started up as a partnership driven by the private sector with the community as the main beneficiary. Service delivery should be commercially viable but may require early subsidies or price controls. Such a model would be appropriate to meet the energy needs of the under-served in rural areas with no access to the grid. This approach is demand-driven. It encourages and builds on existing local institutions and supports the growth of new institutions that can manage and provide the energy services in the long term. It is based on an energy supply option that is most appropriate to the community's current needs, identified by the community itself.

Ensure that disadvantaged communities are reached

Most purely business-based development interventions - including so-called base of the pyramid approaches - are unable to reach the poorest or most isolated communities, due to the nature of markets and the profit margins involved (Wilson *et al.*, 2008). As a result, these communities are often overlooked and remain dependent on unsustainable aid interventions, or on the government, which frequently fails to fulfill its social obligations. Partnering with local governments, donors, NGOs and social enterprises can provide opportunities to reach the poorer communities.

Ensuring the flow of information

Both rural and urban communities have limited access to information on sustainable energy options that are economically feasible. There is a lack of knowledge of the market potential and the potential for providing services to customers, how to replicate projects, identifying financial partners, and the means for creating and maintaining renewable energy systems. There is also a lack of awareness in communities about options for energy provision. Consumers often prefer and expect connection to the electricity grid, because they have limited understanding of the benefits of off-grid systems.

It is difficult to find out what oil and gas companies are doing in this area. There is no central platform for getting information on ongoing projects, opportunities, what has worked and what has not. Emerging initiatives with good potential are not well broadcast and marketed. This is due to poor communication practice rather than competitive secrecy. No one has the time to keep others updated, and it is not perceived as a priority. Basic monitoring and evaluation is also lacking, many of these issues relate to capacity.

Establishing monitoring and evaluation systems

Good quality monitoring and evaluation are essential for all development projects, including energy service provision for low-income communities. Clearly defined monitoring and evaluation methodologies are required to provide rigorous, systematic evidence of the impacts of business-based energy service delivery initiatives on the lives of local consumers, enterprises, and communities overall (Kasturi Rangan *et al.*, 2007). The environmental, social and economic implications of an initiative all need to be taken into consideration from the inception of project. Assessments of needs/opportunities, impacts and risks need to be carried out.

Tackling corruption, funds management and security issues

In January 2008 the Nigerian House of Representatives opened an investigation into allegations of handle Inisuse of power sector funds between 2000 and 2007. The figure in question ranges from USD 4 to USD 10 billion. The investigation claims that under the former President Olusegun Obasanjo, funds earmarked for improved capacity in the power sector were mismanaged and contracts were issued to non-existent companies for IPP projects. The former president had set a target of 10,000MW generating capacity by 2007, whereas the reality is that generating capacity had actually fallen to 3,500MW by the end of 2007.

There is also concern about the use of oil and gas industry revenues. The Nigerian Extractive Industries Transparency Initiative (NEITI) has helped to bring stakeholders in Nigeria together around the issue of transparency of revenue distribution. This initiative and the related Publish What You Pay campaign call for oil and gas companies to publish the revenues that they provide to national governments, and for governments to publish what they receive. NEITI has galvanized civil society action around revenue management. However, NEITI does not extend to transparency of revenue distribution within the country. Civil society organizations have been calling for this and same initiatives are beginning to work on financial management capacity building for local governments.

Transparency of social investment spending

A major concern about both mandatory and voluntary social investment is that the spending is generally not transparent. Frequently, considerable mismanagement and corruption is involved in the spending. This includes the use of local contractors and their connections with local power holders and other political interests. NEITI does not apply to social investment funds. Robust funds management and contracting systems need to be established. Processes need to be transparent and contracts need to be properly managed. Effective monitoring need to be in place. Theft of equipment and security of company staff can be an issue in the Niger Delta. Local governments need to be encouraged to take responsibility for security of community projects-capacity building and collaborative efforts may be required here.

CONCLUSION

Energy deficiency limits peoples development and their heavy dependency on traditional biomass is accompanied by problems of ill-health and environmental degradation. Finding a feasible way to address the energy problems of the poor is a crucial pre-condition for their development and for protection of the environment.

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